

Combined Topics - Covid

1 = Anti-Muslim

01 Anti-Muslim, general ('Muslims are [negative trait]')

02 Anti-Muslim, specific (extremism, evil, radicalisation, anti-Quran, anti-Islamic scripture etc)

03 Islamist Terrorism

04 Islamification/ spread of Islam (Cultural clash, censorship, Islam taking over the world, conversion, attacks on 'our' culture, country, Shariah law, references to the movement of refugees, Muslim problem, cultural deviance)

05 Muslims scapegoated for Coronavirus (including not following restrictions)

07 Islamophobia is denied/exaggerated/playing the victim

2 = Pro-right agendas

25 Pro conservative/right agendas

28 Anti liberal/ left agendas / anti 'woke'

33 Right-wing criticism of mainstream media

34 Tweet disseminates/premised on conspiracy theory

3 = General Covid disruption/Information

06 Changes/ disruption to Muslims' practices, celebrations due to Covid/ Covid measures affecting this

09 Public information tweets/ Instructions (add scientific breakthroughs to this that are not Muslim related which will go in 12)

10 The impact and spread of Covid (specifically funerals and reporting the death toll and spread of Coronavirus in terms of volume)

31 Protest

40 Easing Restrictions

4 = Discrimination towards Muslims/Islamophobia/defending Muslims

08 Disputing that Covid is spread by Muslims

11 Pro-Muslim, general ('Muslims are [positive trait]')

12 Pro-Muslim, specific (contribution to society, acts of kindness, religion of peace, scientific endeavours etc)

13 Anti-Muslim discrimination/racism/ Islamophobia/ attacks on Muslims

18 Muslim celebrations (other than disruption/ changes to which should be coded as 06)

32 Commentary on anti-Muslim propaganda including the media

38 Non-Muslims breaking restrictions

5 = Pro left agendas

26 Anti conservative/right agendas

27 Pro liberal/ left agendas

35 Tweet identifies/alleges conspiracy theory

6 = Condolences/Support

15 Covid heroes (Medical and other emergency staff otherwise goes in 12 or non-Muslim?)

16 Covid victims (Profiles of victims)

17 Expressions of faith/prayers

30 Community relations/cohesion

7 = Covid and International politics/ Global politics

19 Coronavirus and British politics

20 Coronavirus and US politics

21 Coronavirus and Indian politics

22 Coronavirus and global politics

23 International relations

24 Politics, general/other

8 = Other forms of discrimination

14. Anti-Hindu propaganda

29 Immigration/deportation

36 accusation of antisemitism

37 antisemitism in content

39 Anti-Hindi discrimination

99 Other

